

endo- and exo-cyclic nitrogen atoms are not bonded to the metal ions. In the nitrate complexes, absorption bands appear in the region ~ 1280 and 1400 cm^{-1} . The position of ν_4 and ν_1 and their separation ($\Delta\nu$) of $\sim 120\text{ cm}^{-1}$ suggest⁵⁻⁷ the nitrate group to be monodentate in the two complexes. The thiocyanato complexes have two sharp bands at ~ 2080 and 735 cm^{-1} attributable^{8,9} to $\nu(\text{C}\equiv\text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{C}-\text{S})$ vibrations, respectively of N-bonded terminal thiocyanato group. In the present investigation, an increase of $30-40\text{ cm}^{-1}$ relative to the free thiocyanate ion is indicative of N-bonded terminal thiocyanate group on the basis of previous observations¹⁰. The appearance of a broad hump in the region $1040-1150\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicates¹¹⁻¹³ the presence of ionic perchlorate group in the two perchlorate complexes and this is also corroborated by the molar conductance data of these complexes.

The chloro-, nitrate- and thiocyanato complexes are found to be diamagnetic. The perchlorate complexes have high magnetic moments (3.6 to 3.8 B. M.) indicating¹⁴ a tetrahedral environment.

Visible electronic spectra of the chloro-, nitrate- and thiocyanato nickel(II) complexes show absorption bands at ~ 19800 and 20000 cm^{-1} and have relatively high extinction coefficient values, indicative of a square configuration. In case of the perchlorate complexes, two bands are observed at $\sim 15200(180)$ and $8100(35)\text{ cm}^{-1}$ attributable to ${}^3\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F})\rightarrow{}^3\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$ and ${}^3\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F})\rightarrow{}^3\text{A}_{2g}$ transitions, respectively. The high molar absorptivity values of the former band and the high magnetic moment values suggest¹⁵ a possible tetrahedral geometry for the two complexes.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (R. P. M.) is indebted to Dr. D. C. Pati, Department of Chemistry, B. J. B. College, Bhubaneswar for help.

References

1. RAJENDRA P. MISRA, BIPIN B. MOHAPATRA and S. GURU, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, 56, 832.
2. RAJENDRA P. MISRA, BIPIN B. MOHAPATRA and S. GURU, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, 58, 809.
3. J. L. WOOD, "Inorganic Reactions", (Ed.) ROGER ADAMS, 1959, Vol. 3, p. 240.
4. N. C. MISHRA, B. B. MOHAPATRA and S. GURU, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, 55, 437.
5. R. V. BIAGETTI, W. C. BOTTJER and H. M. HANDLER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, 5, 879.
6. N. LOGAN and W. SIMPSON, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1966, 21, 857.
7. A. B. P. LEVER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1935, 4, 1042.
8. K. SWAMINATHAN and H. M. N. H. IRVING, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1962, 26, 1291.
9. A. TURCO and C. PRICILE, *Nature*, 1961, 191, 66.
10. A. TRAMER, *J. Chim. Phys.*, 1962, 59, 282.
11. G. DWYER, J. G. HARTLEY and L. M. VENANZI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, (A), 1965, 1295.
12. K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Wiley, New York, 1970.
13. J. GOPALKRISHNA, A. RAVI and C. C. PATEL, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1967, 40, 791.
14. F. A. COTTON and G. WILKINSON, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", Interscience, 2nd Edn., 1966, 884.

15. P. K. PANDA and B. K. MOHAPATRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 57, 229.
16. D. M. L. GOODGAME, M. GOODGAME and F. A. COTTON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 83, 4161.

Complexes of Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) with Chelating Bidentate Schiff's Base

BEPIN B. MAHAPATRA*, S. M. MAHAPATRA,
S. K. PUJARI and A. CHIRANJEEVI

Post-Graduate Department of Chemistry, G. M. College,
Sambalpur-768 004

Manuscript received 22 May 1981, revised 2 December 1981,
accepted 23 May 1982

WE have been trying to synthesise complexes of rare coordination number through complexation of polydentate ligands with divalent metal salts. Earlier, we reported¹⁻³ metal complexes with bi-, tri- and tetradentate ligands having oxygen-nitrogen oxygen-sulphur, nitrogen-sulphur and oxygen-nitrogen-sulphur as the potential bonding sites. The present communication describes the synthesis and characterisation of six metal complexes with a new bidentate Schiff's base derived from benzoin and aniline.

Experimental

All the chemicals were analytical reagent grade products.

Preparation of the Schiff's base : To a methanolic solution of benzoin (2.12 g) and aniline (1.0 ml) was added anhydrous sodium acetate (4.0 g) and the mixture was refluxed for 1 hr over a water bath. The hot solution was poured into ice-cold water when a yellowish crystalline precipitate of the Schiff's base separated out. It was filtered, washed with water, dried and recrystallised from rectified spirit, m. p. 130° , yield 60%. (Found : C, 82.64; H, 5.52; N, 4.84. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{16}\text{ON}$ requires C, 83.91; H, 5.59; N, 4.89%).

Preparation of the complexes : Ethanolic solutions of the metallic chlorides were treated separately with ethanolic solution of the Schiff's base in 1 : 2 molar ratio followed by drop-wise addition of ammonia when metallic chelates separated out. These were filtered, washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried *in vacuo*.

Metal content of the complexes was estimated by complexometric EDTA titration method. The conductance measurements were carried out with a Toshniwal conductivity bridge in $1 \times 10^{-3}\text{ M}$ acetone solution of the complexes. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made at room temperature using Gouy method. Electronic spectra were recorded in $1 \times 10^{-3}\text{ M}$ chloroform solution of the complexes using Hilger Watt Uvispeck spectrophotometer. The infrared spectra on Nujol mulls

NOTES

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS, CONDUCTANCE, MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY AND IR SPECTRAL DATA

Compound	m.p. °C	Colour	% metal Found (Calcd.)	% N Found (Calcd.)	Λ_M mhos cm ²	μ_{eff} B.M.	$\nu(C-O)$	$\nu(C=N)$
LH	130	Yellow	—	4.85 (4.89)	—	—	1210	1600
CoL ₂ B ₂	142	Pink	8.81 (8.86)	4.17 (4.21)	14.5	4.85	1200	1590
NiL ₂ B ₂	280	Light green	8.75 (8.82)	4.18 (4.22)	12.0	3.00	1200	1585
CuL ₂	251	Blue	9.92 (10.08)	4.38 (4.41)	10.5	1.8	1205	1590
ZnL ₂	224	White	10.15 (10.28)	4.35 (4.40)	15.0	—	1200	1590
CdL ₂	122	White	16.98 (16.47)	3.95 (4.10)	12.5	—	1200	1590
HgL ₂	125	Yellowish white	25.76 (26.08)	3.52 (3.63)	10.0	—	1205	1595

LH = Schiff's base derived from benzoin and aniline.

B = H₂O.

were recorded using Unicam SP 200 spectrophotometer in the region 4000-650 cm⁻¹. Analytical, conductance, magnetic susceptibility and ir spectral data are recorded in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

Complexes reported in the present investigation have the composition [ML₂B₂] and [M'L₂] where M = Co(II), Ni(II); M' = Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II), Hg(II); LH = Schiff's base derived from benzoin and aniline and B = H₂O. All the six complexes have fairly low melting points and low conductance values (Table 1), indicating their non-electrolytic nature. Magnetic moment values show the presence of three, two and one unpaired electrons in case of Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) complexes, respectively.

The ir spectra of the Schiff's base and the metal complexes are quite illustrative. It can function as a bidentate ligand with the hydroxy oxygen and the imino nitrogen atom as the principal bonding sites. The $\nu(C-O)$ vibration in the ligand appears at 1210 cm⁻¹. The decrease of this frequency by 10-15 cm⁻¹ in the metal chelate shows the bonding of the hydroxylic oxygen atom to the metal ions. Coordination of the azomethine nitrogen atom to the metal ions is probably indicated by the shift of $\nu(C=N)$ frequency to the lower side⁹. In the ir spectra of the Schiff's base, a strong band due to $\nu(C=N)$ appears at 1600 cm⁻¹ whereas in the complexes this band is observed at ~1500 cm⁻¹. In case of Co(II) and Ni(II) complexes, a broad hump is observed at ~3450 cm⁻¹ indicating the presence of coordinated water^{10,11}.

In the electronic spectra of Ni(II) complex, three bands appear at 8.5(7), 13.5(7.5) and 25.0(18) kK region, assignable to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions, respectively. Cobalt(II) complex exhibits two absorption bands at 21(26) and 9.0(10) kK regions attributable to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ transitions,

respectively. Molar absorptivity values, position of absorption bands and magnetic moment values indicate high spin octahedral configuration for these complexes. One broad band is observed in case of Cu(II) complex at ~17.0(30) kK region. This broad band is a combination of ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$, ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_{1g}$ transitions corresponding to D_{4h} symmetry, indicating most probably a square planar configuration¹²⁻¹⁴ for this complex.

From analysis, conductance and ir spectral studies, Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) complexes are found to be four coordinated having a tetrahedral environment around the metal ions.

References

1. B. B. MAHAPATRA, B. K. MAHAPATRA and S. GURU, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1977, 39, 2291.
2. B. B. MAHAPATRA, B. K. MAHAPATRA and S. GURU, *Acta Chimica*, 1977, 94, 191.
3. B. B. MAHAPATRA, B. K. MAHAPATRA and S. GURU, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1978, 40, 134.
4. B. B. MAHAPATRA, B. K. MAHAPATRA and S. GURU, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1978, 16A, 445.
5. B. B. MAHAPATRA, B. K. MAHAPATRA and S. GURU, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1978, 16A, 992.
6. B. B. MAHAPATRA, B. K. MAHAPATRA and S. GURU, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, 55, 839.
7. B. B. MAHAPATRA, N. C. MISRA and S. GURU, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1979, 41, 408.
8. B. B. MAHAPATRA, S. S. DASH and S. K. PUJARI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 57, 96.
9. J. E. COVACIS, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1967, 23(A), 188.
10. K. NAKAMATO, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", John Wiley, New York, 1963.
11. I. GAMAQ, *Bull. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1961, 34, 760.
12. J. BJERRUM, O. J. BALLAÜSEN and C. K. JØRGENSEN, *Acta Chim. Scand.*, 1954, 8, 1275.
13. O. J. BALLAÜSEN, "Introduction to Ligand Field Theory", McGraw Hill Book Company, Inc., N. Y., 1962, p. 268.
14. W. BYRERS, A. B. P. LEVER and R. V. PARISH, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, 1, 1885.